

Land Use Transformations Project (JHI-C3-1)
Milestone 7 – Land Use/Land Use Change Governance Analysis
Methodology
Internal Report

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1 Overview

This is the first part of the **LU/LUC Governance Analysis** (screening LUC policies for objectives, instruments, implementation and their actors). Our milestone is to agree the Policy Coherence Methodology with SRUC. This internal document sets out the agreed conceptual approach and summarises the decisions made about the planned methodology.

An initial rapid screening will be used to help support the Phase 1 Quantitative Story Telling (QST1) cycle for the [Land Use Transformations](#) project (JHI C3-1) taking place September 2022 – March 2023. Intention for QST1 is being summarised in Milestone 12 (an internal report capturing intentions for QST1), building on learning from Phase 0 QST (QST0), reported in the [State of Play](#) document (Milestone 10) and a formal decision of the QST1 focus (screening enhanced conditionality measures) is being finalised with RESAS (Milestone 5).

The aim is to complete the screening by end of November if possible.

The next phase of the LU/LUC Governance Analysis starts in January 2023 for over a year with later milestones to align with QST cycles and D11 Journal paper on governing LU/LUC at scale and pace (due October 2025).

2 Conceptual approach

2.1 What is Land Use?

- How land is used to produce provisioning ecosystem services; also how it is managed to produce regulating, supporting and cultural ecosystem services.
- However, there is a whole range of issues around 'land' that will be relevant to change and transformation – use is influenced by issues like land rights and land tenure; but also land cover, land management and social acceptability of landscape character might be relevant to achieving net zero & env goals.
- We are focussed on rural land not all land.
- Therefore, we will include how the following sectors use (manage, access) land: agriculture, forestry, sporting, energy, conservation & associated recreation/tourism.
- We do not directly include freshwater use, but catchment management highlights how land use/management has influences on water & water influences land use (especially droughts/floods) – so water becomes one of the main environmental goals (see below).

2.2 What is policy coherence?

- Policy coherence focusses on whether multiple separate policies working towards the same or similar overall objectives are consistent or generate unintended conflicts or contradictions (Nilsson et al., 2012).
- Policy can be conceptualized in terms of different levels (Tier 1 and Tier 2 **objectives** set out in legislation, steering strategies, and policy **instruments**) that are operationalized via a policy cycle moving from design in terms of objectives and instruments, through **implementation**, to monitoring and evaluation processes that may result in policy adaptation or change. The institutions involved in these levels and cycles include interacting actors, resources, interests and ideas. Even using these simplifications, single silo policy analysis can be complex when exploring how levels, cycles and institutions interact over time and space, forming different regimes and coalitions (Cairney & Geyer, 2017).
- This complexity increases when policy coherence is being analyzed, requiring a simultaneous understanding of vertical and horizontal coherence.

Vertical coherence refers to coherence between the overall policy objectives and scope, the policy instruments by which such objectives can be achieved (rules, incentives, information, actions), and the policy implementation processes by which these instruments are animated by actors.

Horizontal coherence is between parallel policy objectives, instruments, and implementation processes.

During discussions we anticipate a new type – **diagonal coherence** – whereby the objective of one policy is explicitly designed to be delivered by the instruments and implementation associated with another policy.

- We use an interpretative policy analysis that recognises the importance of context, history & different perspectives (see Figure 1, (Blackstock et al., 2018)). For our purposes, we will drop the focus on history and different perspectives.

Figure 1: Policy Coherence Framework (adapted from Blackstock et al. 2018)

2.3 How does this relate to governance?

- Governance refers to all processes of governing, the institutions, processes and practices through which issues of common concern are decided upon and regulated¹.
- Generally academic definitions of ‘good’ governance will include issues associated with legitimacy and power effects.
- Governance therefore draws particular attention to the actors and practices involved in policy coherence.

2.4 How does this relate to Research Question 2 from the Call?

- RQ2: **How can we make more effective use of land by joining up approaches to managing land for different uses, and across larger scales?**
- This is in the context of achieving net zero and ‘other environmental goals’.

¹ <https://www.ohchr.org/en/good-governance/about-good-governance>

- For net zero we will include both agriculture and land use chapters of Climate Change Plan; and
- ‘Other environmental goals’ will be based on objectives noted in the Land Use Strategy, the Environment Strategy, River Basin Management Plan, Biodiversity Strategy.

2.5 Outline Research Questions?

- Are there synergies, gaps or conflicts in the way current LU policies are supporting LU transformation?
- Are there problems of vertical, diagonal and/or horizontal coherence within existing LU policies?
- Does coherence explain the ability to deliver LU Transformation?
- What are the opportunities to improve or sustain coherence? [i.e. where there is coherence, how do we strengthen it and roll it out, and where there is conflict, how do we reduce it]
- How can coherence be monitored more effectively in the future?

3 Our proposed process

3.1 Excel Matrix

We agreed that we will use a **common spreadsheet matrix** to consider policy coherence for land use change/transformations – trying to get a balance between setting up a rigorous process with clear criteria about what to include or exclude; and how to evaluate things whilst not chewing up too much resource so that we do not have to time to use the findings.

We will have one row per policy (single document or set of closely related documents).

We will have columns with drop down menus to assign a category to these documents. A companion column will have a short justification for the choice of category.

We will have a sheet for whether policies advance LU transformations; and a sheet for coherence.

3.2 Land Use Transformation Goals

- We agreed to focus on **‘goals of land use transformation’** and identify some strategic transformation goals that sit at the heart of Scottish LU and environmental policy to guide our screening process.
- These ‘desired net zero and environmental outcomes from land use and land use change’ will be developed from a set of foundational policies (e.g. Climate Change Plan, Land Use Strategy, River and Biodiversity Strategies, Environmental Strategy). It will be updated based on 2022 Programme for government [to be actioned]
- These strategic goals would sit above the top-level ‘policy’ structure in Figure 1 and allow us to consider in what ways the different dimensions of policies contribute to these overall goals.

3.3 Using the Matrix

- The spreadsheet will act as a screening matrix for a ‘longlist’ of policies that have been identified as relevant to land use or land use change.
- A ‘longlist’ of potential policies to include in the screening process was created in June 2022; and has been updated from an online search.

- a. Question about how to handle proposed relevant Bills (New Agriculture Bill out for consultation August 22, Land Reform Bill out for consultation July 22). Normally would only include finalised policies but these are essential to the QST process.
 - b. Question about how to bundle connected documents (e.g. the consultation documents, vision statements and working group reports related to the Future Agriculture bill).
- The approach will be a simple yes/no screening to visualise the main patterns and identify areas to analyse in more detail. Further analysis will consider the reasons for any patterns developed.
- We suggest having two sheets – one focused on contribution to the LUT goals and one focussed on coherence. Understanding coherence can help explain how the goals can be achieved and the goals provide the rationale for coherence. However, trying to do both at once in the same sheet may get confusing.
- The individual policies will **FIRST** be considered regarding whether these policies contribute to one or more of the **‘goals of land use transformation’**
 - a. This will be done first to establish a rapid overview of whether all aspects of transformation are being supported
 - b. Use of colour coded cells to help visualise patterns
 - c. This will happen in one excel sheet.
 - d. One column for Y/N – does the policy support this goal? and one column to record reason for Y/N decision for each goal and an overall summative column – does this policy advance LU Transformations (Y/N) with companion column to explain this answer.
 - e. The screening could also consider by when the goals should be achieved, use of any quantified targets, and whether the outcomes are expected everywhere or only for certain geographies or social groups.
 - f. We will need to pilot the approach with each of us filling in a row and checking how it works and if we are consistent.
 - g. Then we can each take a set of rows to input; and we will cross-check a sample of other rows to ensure we are being consistent.
 - h. The end point will be to highlight if all LUT goals are being addressed equally; and where there are any imbalances or gaps.
 - We can check by types of governance instrument, topic or other attribute to see if there are any patterns.
 - It will also start to highlight where there are **horizontal coherence** relationships where the same policies are all expected to support one or more LUT goals. These relationships can be further developed in the 2nd sheet.
- Each policy will **SECONDLY** be considered in terms of whether it **coheres vertically** (to explain if the intention to deliver to the goals might be prevented due to not having sufficient instruments or implementation)
 - a. Each policy will be summarised in terms of its objectives, their enacting instruments, and information about where/how/with whom they are implemented to establish their **vertical coherence**.
 - b. Where when policy references another policy that is involved in delivering an objective (**diagonal coherence**), this link will be captured using excel functionality [hyperlinks]

- c. The links between policies will be addressed to see if they **cohere horizontally** (to explain if the intention to deliver to the goals might be prevented due to incoherence or gaps between policies) – this analysis will start from the clusters of policies all contributing to the same LUT goals, but also to see if there are coherence synergies and conflict that are not directly related to these LUT goals.
- Further analysis will explore the policies in terms of wider criteria highlighted in the box:

Criteria (attribute data):

Examples include:

- Scale of the policy (national, regional, local, all land/specific land, farm types, etc.)
- Requirement for collaboration or working beyond individual businesses
- Each policy will relate to a particular topic (e.g. water, forestry, etc.).
- Whether quantified and/or time limited targets are set?
- Who is accountable for these goals or how is progress reported?

- The analysis will allow the team to offer concrete and brief recommendations in relation to:
 - a. Are there gaps or conflicts in the way current LU policies are supporting LU transformation?
 - b. Are there problems of vertical, diagonal and/or horizontal coherence?
 - c. Does coherence explain the ability to deliver LU Transformation?
 - d. What are the opportunities to improve or sustain coherence? [i.e. where there is coherence, how do we strengthen it and roll it out, and where there is conflict, how do we reduce it]
 - e. How can coherence be monitored more effectively in the future?

4 Next steps

- The spreadsheet matrix will be refined in September 2022. This will include consideration of how to incorporate both scoring data in the analysis, alongside qualitative notes about the decisions we make during the analysis; and how the excel data can be used in NVIVO for deeper analysis in the next phase.
- The 'longlist' will be refined during September.
- We will start the screening process in October and finish by the end of November 2022.
- We will keep exploring what governance arrangements are steering the policy coherence, which might include some scoping interviews.

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